

Creating Safe Spaces For All Children: Transactional Read-Alouds In The Early Childhood Classroom

Kerry Rizzuto

Article Info	Abstract
<i>Article History</i>	<i>A Vignette of a Transactional Read-Aloud</i>
Received: January 20,2025	<i>In Emma's Kindergarten class, three students were born in Mexico; four students were born in Honduras; and another four children were born in the United States., however, their parents are immigrants from Mexico, Guatemala, and Honduras. These students speak Spanish with varying degrees of English proficiency and have direct or indirect experiences with the immigration process, and some have relatives whose status is currently unknown. The remainder of the class is comprised of five monolingual native English speakers.</i>
Accepted: April 22,2025	<i>Emma begins each day with a transactional read-aloud. Today, she has selected to read Migrant by Maxine Trottier. This book features Anna, a child of Mennonites from Mexico, who migrate north in the spring to harvest fruits and vegetables and then return south in the fall. Throughout the book, Emma points to the illustrations, which depict Anna's longing to feel deeply rooted in the earth, watching the seasons come and go. The text expresses the character's yearning to live in one place, forever.</i>
Keywords : Kindergarten, Children, Students, English Speakers	<i>During the read-aloud, Emma purposefully points out the illustrations, which support the themes of the story. For example, at various points in the story, Anna feels like a jackrabbit in an abandoned burrow because her family occupies an empty farmhouse near the fields, and sometimes like a kitten, as she shares a bed with her sisters. During the read-aloud, Emma relates her own experiences with her class, "When I was young, my sisters and I slept in one bed. We thought that we were like a pack of small puppies, snuggled up together, especially on the nights when my mother came in and slept." Emma can draw a picture of her shared anecdote with the class and write the words out on a large chart paper, creating an interactive writing experience.</i>
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15263543	<i>Emma allows time for spontaneous reactions from the students, verbally or through drawing and writing. When Emma first introduced the transactional read-aloud, she provided her students with appropriate writing paper for early childhood students, as well as pencils or crayons. It takes time for all students to feel comfortable sharing; therefore, Emma is consistent with her instruction. By sharing her own experiences and reactions to the book, she creates a classroom where children are comfortable taking emotional and academic risks.</i>
	<i>As Emma continues to read-aloud, Marc softly says, "I miss my dad." Maria turns to him and responds, "I know, I get scared a lot, too." At this point, Emma asks the children if they would like to have a few moments to speak to each other or draw and write. During these five minutes, one child approaches Emma and asks to look at the pictures. Then, he begins to illustrate a story and writes a few words next to it. Emma quietly asks him if he wants to share; however, he tells her that he will "think about it."</i>

Introduction

Shifts in demographics are changing the face of the world. In 2020, the total number of people forcibly displaced from their homes rose to 72.5 million, with 28.3 million categorized as refugees (United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees [UNHCR], 2020). Additionally, the United States public school system is undergoing a "demographic milestone" (Education Week, 2018). The Pew Research Center states that one out of every four children in the United States is an immigrant or the U.S. born child of immigrants, and by 2040, a third of the nation's school children younger than 17 will either be immigrants themselves or the children of at least one parent who is one. To address this demographic milestone, schools will need to rethink classroom

strategies, family engagement practices, and how to best navigate cultural divides. According to Manning (2018), improving race relations and attenuating stereotypes based on immigration should be a primary goal for all schools.

Refugee and immigrant children's educational needs differ from those of other students; many of these children have experienced trauma and frequent interruptions to their education (Crawford & Donner, 2018). Public schools and educators are uniquely positioned to provide support for immigrant students. The U.S. National Teacher of the Year for 2018, Mandy Manning, spoke at the recent Migration Policy Institute conference. Manning (2018) stated, "Teachers need to be compassionate and open to the needs of immigrant and refugee students and create instruction that reflects their needs" (p. 7). Further, Manning (2018) described an ongoing situation in her school in which students have been asking when they or their parents will be forced to leave the country. These issues must be addressed both in policy and in the curriculum by the schools.

Nationwide, 1.6 million children under the age of five have at least one undocumented parent (Gándara & Ee, 2018, p. 3). Many of these young immigrant children are entering schools for the first time, which tends to be a difficult transition because they are typically connected to their families and may have shared traumatic experiences [The National Association for the Education of Young Children] (NAEYC, 2018). The climate in today's schools for many children and their families is one of fear; many of these fears are not entirely unfounded. Despite a policy prohibiting engagement in immigration enforcement in schools (U.S. Department of Homeland Security, U.S. Immigration and Custom Enforcement, October 2020), numerous incidents have been reported (Rein, Hauslohner, & Somashekhar, 2017). For example, planned enforcement action was carried out during morning drop-off "in plain view of students and families" (Phillips, 2017). The potential reach of these concerns is substantial. Gándara and Ee (2018) estimated that more than 5 million children in U.S. cities reside with parents affected by U.S. immigration policies. They reported that 53% of respondents who completed their survey ($N = 3800$) said parental fear of immigration enforcement authorities.

Immigrant children have reported their biggest fear is losing their parents; some children may have already experienced a family member's loss. Early childhood experiences contribute to young children's sense of self-efficacy about their ability to succeed in school. Children who are immigrants may be especially vulnerable during these early schooling experiences as they are only beginning to develop an understanding of how they fit into their family, culture, and community. Furthermore, many young children of immigrants may face negative school biases during this formative period (Hoffman, 2017).

Research suggests that students who are confident in their cultural and ethnic identity can buffer the impact of discrimination on their well-being (Gamboa, Lilley & Calhan, 2020; Hattan & Lupo, 2020). Recent media attention to the global humanitarian crisis has emphasized the importance of creating inclusive and multicultural experiences, both inside and outside the classroom, to serve the diverse student populations attending our schools (Ward & Warren, 2020), as the practices that schools adopt can ameliorate negative outcomes for immigrant children. A specific and targeted way to achieve this goal is to adopt cultural responsive literacy instruction. Such practices can range from choosing multicultural books to be featured in classroom libraries to the discussions that teachers have about books with their students.

Researchers who study children's literature have articulated the need for using a critical lens to examine the books teachers choose for read-aloud sessions. Au (2011) encourages teachers to reflect on the following when choosing books: who does the telling in the story? Who are the stories about? and who (or what groups) get left out? These questions align with Vygotsky and social constructivism when teaching reading. Souto-Manning uses sociocultural theory to demonstrate that meaning is more than a cognitive act; it is instead socially and culturally constructed. Comprehension involves three elements influenced by the sociocultural context: the reader, the text and the activity of reading itself.

When teachers adopt a sociocultural perspective in their classroom literacy instruction, they include multicultural literacy practices, emphasizing the fundamental role of the social context in academic and social development (Vaquez, 2017). Another important aspect of Vygotsky's views on learning is the significance of language in the learning process. Embracing a sociocultural perspective in the multicultural class enables dual language learners to use their cultural backgrounds when learning language and honoring their first language, in situated contexts as language emerges and develops (Bathkin, 1986).

Teachers of students who are ELLs or have immigrant backgrounds must be intentional about supporting their success in U.S. schools. One way that teachers can ensure success is to make sure that these children are represented in the classroom library (García & Kleifgen, 2018). Furthermore, when teachers are mindful to choose books to echo their student's backgrounds, the stories can act as mirrors, recreating and reflecting immigrant students' personal experiences in alignment with sociocultural and multicultural theory. (Souto-Manning, 2020). During the transactions between books and readers, when students see their own lives in the books that are read to them, they are more likely to feel included in the classroom and the larger world. One way to encourage immigrant and refugee students' cultural confidence is through transactional read-alouds.

Purpose

The purpose of this paper is to explore the place of the multicultural transactional read-aloud in the classroom. In addition to understanding its instructional tenets and strategies required to incorporate it, this paper will help teachers find specific areas within the curricula to enhance and build upon their existing literacy instruction. Now more than ever before, teachers must adjust their literacy and language practices to meet the needs of children whose home and school experiences are vastly different (Au, 2011; Cummins, 2001; García & Kleifgen 2018).

Utilizing sociocultural theory, educators could expand upon and reframe “the knowledge gap,” (Hattan & Lupo, 2020, p. 13). Educators should be thinking about the cultural, languages, and, experiences of the students in their classrooms, to consider how students’ prior knowledge will be activated and combined during literacy instruction. Towards that pursuit, Souto-Manning (2020) suggests teachers infuse multicultural literacy into their instruction. Immigrants and refugee students – all students’ lives - can be changed by reading diverse literature. Additionally, teachers who adopt a sociocultural worldview can help us advocate for change that goes beyond the classroom.

Multicultural classrooms play a significant part in helping immigrant and refugee students develop language learning through sociocultural interactions. Learning a language together fosters social integration. It helps students engage in conversations with their peers; however, teachers should make a note to create safe spaces in which all children feel emotionally safe to take risks using a new language. Teachers can accomplish this by demonstrating an appreciation of all children's cultures and home languages, using abundant communication in instruction tasks, (e.g., form small peer groups to talk about specific subjects and building students' self-confidence). Language is developed by giving ELL and immigrant students small tasks that they can complete together in pairs; they must speak about the process (e.g., how can we build these blocks to look like those blocks?) Further, working collaboratively on learning tasks is essential in a multicultural class in which students of diverse backgrounds learn how to create a dialogue, solve a problem, and value each other's cultures (Hattan & Lupo, 2020).

This paper covers the following areas:

- 1) Explores how multicultural transactional read-alouds differ from other forms of reading alouds (e.g., the interactive read-aloud);
- 2) Provides suggestions for implementing the transactional read-aloud into the multicultural curriculum and exploration of where it fits into the curriculum; and
- 3) Suggests a list of books conducive to creating a transactional experience and a guideline to selecting multicultural books for future instruction

What makes a read-aloud "Transactional" and how does it differ from other kinds of read-alouds?

The read-aloud is an instructional practice in which teachers read books aloud to children. It is predominantly an early childhood instructional strategy in which the teacher gathers a group of young children together for the reading of a book in order to help them learn aspects of beginning literacy, such as print conventions, print tracking, the concept of a word, and beginning reading strategies. Many times, the books are larger in size (big books), so that children can gather around the teacher, recreating the shared home reading experience. Typically, the teacher incorporates variations in pitch, tone, pace, volume, and ask questions about the book. According to Trelease (2001), reading books aloud is the single most important activity for building the knowledge required for successful reading.

Reading aloud in early childhood classrooms is a standard part of daily classroom instruction. However, often, it is not a literacy practice that emphasizes substantive discussions around the text or critical theory (García & Weiss, 2015). Yet, essential multicultural literacy practices include ways of interacting with powerful texts for the reader (Morrow, 2014). Sociocultural perspectives of literacy (e.g., Adams, 1998; Morrow, 2014; Vasquez, 2017) suggest that writing, reading, and language are not decontextualized skills, separate from specific contexts, contents, and social-communication purposes. Most current multicultural literacy views share Vygotsky's (1978) theory that all learning is socially and culturally transmitted and advocates for a multidimensional dialogue among the text, the content, and the reader. Creating literacy instruction from a critical perspective requires recognizing diverse personal and cultural viewpoints and allowing students to have meaningful dialogue, hence the transactional read-aloud.

In the transformative read-aloud, there is a shift in the dialogic discourse, because teachers share the agency with the children (Lenox, 2013). Children and teacher as well child-to-child engage in reciprocal conversations. These conversations are generated as the teacher reads the book; at a certain point in the book, the teacher may prompt the class, or a child may raise her hand to offer a thought or a question. The teacher may give the class time to speak in dyads or time for some children to write or draw alone, giving them time to express themselves.

A transactional read-aloud includes the uses of language that invites children to reflect on their own lives to create a multicultural classroom in which they feel understood (Coehlo, 2012). The kind of phrases included in this type of read-aloud include: Let's stop and think, have you ever felt the way that this character

has?; did this book remind you of something that you have experienced?; should we stop and take a minute to talk about it, or write about it?; and does anyone want to write or draw about it? Importantly, transactional read-alouds encourage immigrant and refugee students' cultural confidence, because these read-alouds are crafted for the participation of ELLs and immigrants.

During any reading experience, printed words are essential. Rosenblatt (1985) maintained that comprehension results from the transaction between the reader and the written word. She held that the reader's knowledge and experiences to making meaning from the text are at the heart of creating authentic literacy instruction. To apply transactional theory, teachers must show students how to use what they read and what they know to build meaning. Typically, when an early childhood teacher plans a transactional read-aloud, they consider what prior knowledge readers might bring to the book. Teachers choose books that contain plots, characters, and themes that immigrant children find in their homes and can relate to (Warren & Ward, 2020).

Suppose we are to move to a more culturally affirming reality. In that case, teachers need to develop a multicultural curriculum and literacy pedagogy for transformation, one that is characterized by an ongoing effort to create new space for dialogic speech, to rewrite cultural narratives, and to allow for discussion of multiple kinds of literature and perspectives (Hoffman, 2017). Reader response encourages students to become aware of what they bring to texts as readers; it has the potential to help them recognize the specificity of their cultural backgrounds, and strive to understand the cultural backgrounds of others. However, multicultural transformative literacy experiences are capable of doing both simultaneously, promoting intercultural and intracultural understanding (Glazer & Seo, 2011). Bakhtin (1986) advised us that the only way to know ourselves honestly is through the "other"; wholeness emerges in and through that dialogue.

Children require multiple opportunities to talk about the text and vocabulary and, just as importantly, talk about their lives and how to resolve challenges in their lives. Reading in a multicultural classroom can be a haven, especially for children who are immigrants, and a way to better understand themselves and develop a positive identity. For example, here are a few talking points that teachers can stop and use during a transactional read aloud:

- What do you like best about your book?
- What feelings did this book evoke for you?
- Which character do you most closely relate to, and why?
- How have you been changed by what you read?

Also, teachers may want to consider:

- Using different storytelling and creation tools to support the diversity of students;
- Allowing young children to listen to and read books, which might have a positive impact on young children's desire to retell or recreate existing stories or to create their own, and;
- Providing opportunities for children to construct stories, which will also support their narrative learning;

As seen from the above suggestions, a transactional read-aloud extends beyond the reading of the text itself. Therefore, it may be beneficial for teachers to conceptualize this approach as an instructional cycle consisting of pre-, during-, and post-reading activities. As a result, teachers will need to consider instructional strategies for implementation and determine where it best fits the literacy instructional block.

Building teachers' knowledge of how and where to implement the transactional read-aloud

Determining where the transactional read-aloud fits in the curriculum is an essential step for successful integration, yet becoming familiar with the transactional nature of the read aloud may require practice and refinement by teachers to ensure these fit within the classroom climate. According to Johnson, Koss, and Martinez (2017), reading aloud in early childhood classrooms is a standard part of daily classroom instruction. Yet, often this literacy practice may lack rich discussions around the text or critical theory. As a result, students may be unfamiliar with such conversations or reluctant due to a culture of fear.

Further, transactional read-alouds require the thoughtful use of scaffolding. Teachers' use of scaffolds refers to temporarily providing support to learners and then gradually withdrawing this support as the learners become more independent. Book introductions support students as they read texts with increasing difficulty levels and are among the most critical aspects of scaffolding instruction (Adams, 1998; Morrow, 2014; Vasquez, 2017). In a whole-class setting, the teacher may need to use a diverse assortment of scaffolding strategies to meet each student's needs (Pearson & Gallagher, 1983).

The use of multicultural literature, paired with dialogic instruction within a safe classroom culture, provides students with both a window to other cultures and a mirror reflecting their own (Warren & Ward, 2020). Talk is central to the work of teaching and learning in U.S. classrooms (Glazier & Seo, 2011). Indeed, discourse is how we come to acquire and create knowledge of the world and our lives (Bakhtin, 1986). To aid development of second language acquisition in multicultural classrooms, teachers can use peer-groups; some groups can have speakers of the same second language, some may be a mix of language speakers. However, it is important to encourage students to keep using their home language to ensure it remains strong (Au, 2011).

Teachers can model comprehension of and reflection on stories by demonstrating how to slow down

while reading, attend closely, and reflect thoughtfully; readers need to prepare for the discussion and learn to listen to others' responses to extend their understanding (Johnson, Koss, & Martinez, 2017). One way to prepare students to participate actively is to model the process during and after the reading. During-reading responses can guide interpretation, involvement, and understanding based on what students bring to, and take from, the text (Rosenblatt, 1985).

Other instructional considerations are also necessary—for example, transactional read-alouds call for increasing wait-time. Budd-Rowe (1986) maintains that teachers should ask children to directly respond to their peers during the literacy session, which raises critical thought and student involvement. Allowing children to respond to their peers' ideas creates dialogues that are child-centered rather than teacher-directed; this encourages more authentic student expression during the entire school day. Allowing students to become more familiar with self-expression develops their language skills and provides them with practice in sharing their thoughts during transactional read-alouds. Also, by jotting down anecdotal notes of which students are speaking and engaging in conversation during center or free-time as well as noticing *what* students are talking about, teachers can be more aware of their funds of knowledge (Moll & Gonzalez, 1994) and what language skills need to be enhanced.

Teachers might model written responses on large chart paper and invite students to write or draw during pre-selected parts of the book. Student responses can occur during or after reading. Once children are accustomed to the process, the teacher can encourage children to respond freely during the read-aloud. Modeling can be repeated for verbal responses and after-reading responses. As the gradual release of responsibility transfers from teacher to students (Crawford & Donner, 2017; Pearson & Gallagher, 1983), students are invited to write, draw, or speak, prompted by their independent needs.

Additionally, the paired and small-group collaboration provides motivation, which is crucial for immigrant and refugee students. Motivation increases interest and learning of the material for children who, facing harrowing experiences, may be hesitant to participate, even in a welcoming setting such as a multicultural classroom. Moreover, the read-aloud setting can serve as a catalyst to engage students in many activities relevant to language learning goals, which can help children who are learning a second language. Peer-to-peer language interactions are a staple in the multicultural classroom. **language exchanges can be achieved.** However, some immigrant and refugee children come from countries where talk in the classroom is discouraged. Therefore, Cazden (2001) wrote that teachers must scaffold academic language as well as affective language in their classrooms, by providing time for children to speak with each other by prompting children with meaningful topics. This support leads to rich language interactions, which can encourage social relationship and expanded language use.

Additionally, Fountas and Pinnell (2018) suggest that multicultural classroom should include the use of both short and long (leveled or unlevelled) texts that are used for different purposes. Moreover, they suggest that teachers acquire a collection of books, representing the children's diversity in their classrooms. In their multi-text classroom, they present various instructional contexts, including the transformative read-aloud, shared reading, guided reading, book clubs, and independent reading. The use of the transactional read-aloud simply builds on this approach. Students can engage in analytical thinking during the read-alouds, which free the student from the cognitive task of decoding. Interactive discussions provide much-needed meaning-space for children to make profound connections to the stories that they hear (Vasquez, 2017). During these read-alouds, teachers can make space for critical literacy through the books that are read and shared with students. The transactional read-aloud allows for freer student talk, focusing on a discussion on interpretive meaning rather than literal level comprehension.

A suggested book list for transactional read-alouds

A key area to consider in the implementation of transactional read-alouds is book choice. It is vital to consider the ever-changing definition of multicultural children's literature to include more cultural experiences in seeking titles. Traditionally, ethnicity was the element teachers used to consider a book multicultural. Yet, many other occasions need to be shared through the world of children's books (Hoffman, 2017). Consequently, the definition of multicultural literature has been changed to include "people who have historically, ideologically, and politically been underserved and rendered nearly invisible" (Botelho & Rudman, 2009, p.124). Instructional planning for transactional read-alouds and the use of teacher talk is critical. Purposeful prompts are required to spur meaningful discussion. Moreover, the discussion of essential vocabulary and concepts also frame and support the young child's comprehension of the text.

When choosing books to share with your students, consider the following:

- Authentic depiction of the cultural experience
- Accuracy of cultural details in the text and illustrations
- Positive representation of all children's cultures in the class represented

The following is a list of books of may be used to incorporate the transactional read-aloud:

Drawn Together by Minh Lê- A young boy and his grandfather find common ground through art. It is there that language brings them together. This picture book illustrates how to reach across the language barrier and communicate in other ways, along with rich elements of Asian culture.

Dreamers by Yuyi Morales- A mother and her young son leave their country. The story chronicles the difficulties surrounding immigration and the intangible items immigrants bring with them, such as strength and resilience. This picture book memoir provides a rich and detailed rendition of the immigrant experience.

Floating on Mama's Song by Laura Lacamara- Anita's mother is such a wonderful singer that every person who hears her singing begins to float high above the ground. This dual-language picture book celebrates the importance of family and happiness.

Growing up with Tamales by Gwen Zepeda- Ana envies her sister because she is the one who gets to make the tamales every year for Christmas. Ana dreams about the day when she will open her own tamale factory and be able to share her family's tamales with the world. This picture book, which comes in a dual-language format, explores the elements of a sibling relationship and a Latin tradition.

In My Family by Carmen Lomas Garza- Set in Kingsville, Texas, near the Mexico-America border, the story explores the traditions and memories of growing up within the Mexican-American community. The dual-language picture book highlights many rich elements of Mexican-American culture and personal memories of the author.

The Journey by Francesca Sanna- Through the perspective of a young girl, this story details the journey of a refugee family escaping war within their home country. The narrative brings to light the decisions and struggles a family escaping their home country encounters. This picture book sheds light on the refugee experience in a way in which children can understand.

Margaret and Margarita by Lynn Reiser- Margarita only speaks Spanish and Margaret only speaks English but that doesn't stop them from becoming friends. This bilingual picture book explores how two girls who speak different languages are still able to play together despite the language barrier while also introducing words in both English and Spanish.

My Diary from Here to There: Mi diario de aqui hasta alla by Amada Perez- Through her diary, Amanda recounts her feelings and experiences as her family moves from Mexico to Los Angeles. Told in English and Spanish, this story details a young girl's feelings about her father's decision to leave Mexico and search for work in the United States.

The Name Jar by Yangsook Choi- Unhei has just moved to America from Korea and is nervous that other kids won't be able to pronounce her name. The class creates a name jar, full of possible names. However, when it comes time to choose a name, Unhei's friends choose her own name. All of Unhei's friends learn how to pronounce it.

Stella Diaz Has Something to Say by Angela Dominguez- When Stella Diaz's best friend is placed in a different class, Stella is lonely until a new boy arrives in class. She wants to be friends with him, but, Stella accidentally speaks Spanish sometimes and pronounces words wrong. Stella's new friend helps her to accept and love herself and her language.

The Storyteller's Candle / La Velita De Los Cuentos by Lucia Gonzalez- Two cousins, Hildamar and Santiago, have just moved from Puerto Rico to New York and miss their home. When a librarian comes to their classroom, everything changes as the cousins see the value of a library.

We Came to America by Faith Ringgold- This picture book focuses on the diversity of America and the many different people that came to America from different circumstances. The story celebrates the gifts that different cultures brought with them to America and how diversity has shaped the country.

Implications

Research on critical literacies has found that children are entirely capable of engaging in higher-level practices when meaning-making is facilitated by teacher support in a multicultural classroom that includes engaging interactive discussion (Callow, 2017). These studies (e.g., Au, 2011; Goldenberg, 2008; Vasquez, 2017) of higher-level literacy instruction have two common elements: the form of the discourse is student-

centered allowing for freer student talk than is observed in a traditional three-turn teacher initiation, student response, teacher evaluation (IRE) pattern (Goldenberg, 2008). Here, the focus of discussion is on interpretive meaning, which is a key element in multicultural pedagogy. Interactive discussion is crucial to meaning-making with texts because meaning construction is dependent on social interaction and language (Vygotsky, 1978).

Connecting with stories can help children develop a sense of community. According to Huck (1987), "Literature has the power to take us out of ourselves and return us to ourselves a changed self, to enlarge our thinking while educating our hearts" (p. 70). When teachers utilize **transformative** read-alouds, they provide robust and authentic literacy instruction, which develops all children's oral language, reading, and writing skills. Perhaps most importantly, teachers are creating a multicultural classroom culture that reflects understanding and acceptance.

The use of instructional approaches, such as the **transactional** read aloud, fosters the development of children's oral language, reading, and writing skills, yet, perhaps just as important, it provides teachers the opportunity to create a classroom culture that reflects understanding acceptance. So, while the use of this approach might be particularly well-suited to help cultivate a climate of understanding and acceptance for children who may be marginalized due to differences in culture or language, this approach has the potential to support the language and literacy development of all children, as well as their social and emotional development.

Most essentially, in our classrooms, we have students who are refugees and new immigrants to the U.S., each of us is challenged as to how we respond as individuals and as global citizens. As literacy educators, literature plays a role in teaching positive civic and social values in our students (Callow, 2017). We live in a culture in which depictions of refugees and immigrants are often politically charged, ignoring their humanity and perpetuating negative stereotypes (Ward & Warren, 2020). It is here that the role of critical multicultural literacy, as part of our understanding of global literacy, can play an essential role in our classroom learning and teaching.

Stories help us understand the social world in new ways. Miall (2006) labels this process of adopting new perspectives as "to dishabituate," which transcends gender, ethnicity, and reality, and affirms self-concepts. To gain social understanding from fiction, we must consider characters' internal experiences in addition to plot because, "just as in real life, the worlds of literary fiction are replete with complicated individuals whose inner lives are rarely easily discerned but warrant exploration" (Kidd & Castano, 2013, p. 277). Teachers can begin to create these critical literacy practices starting with the classroom read-aloud (Vasquez, 2017).

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Author Information

Kerry Rizzuto
